

**ANTIBACTERIAL EFFECTIVENESS OF HAND SANITIZERS AGAINST
*ESCHERICHIA COLI.***

BY

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**BEING A PROJECT SUBMITTED TO THE DEPARTMENT OF BIOLOGICAL
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SCIENCE DEGREE (B.SC) IN BIOLOGY.**

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DECLARATION

I hereby declared that this research work titled **Antibacterial effectiveness of selected hand sanitizers against *Escherichia coli*** is the product of my own research undertaken under the supervision of **Mal. Abdullahi, Shehu Ado** and has not presented and will not be presented elsewhere for the award of degree. All sources of information have been duly acknowledged.

SAFIYYAH DAHIRU

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Sign and Date

CERTIFICATION

This is to certify that the research work titled **Antibacterial activity of some hand sanitizers against *Escherichia coli*** by **SAFIYYA DAHIRU** with registration number **NAS/BIO/19/3159** was carried out under my supervision.

Mal. Abdullahi Shehu Ado

(Project Supervisor)

Sign and date

Mal. Muhammad A Said

(Head of Department)

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APPROVAL

This project work has been read and approved and it has met the necessary requirements for the award of Bachelor of Science (B.Sc) in Biology, under the supervision of Mal. Abdullahi, Shehu Ado.

Mal. Abdullahi Shehu Ado

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Sign and date

DEDICATION

This project work is whole-heartedly and humbly dedicated to Almighty Allah who has been Merciful, Loving and Protective in directing all of my affairs throughout the period of my studies in Al-Qalam University Katsina. I also dedicated this research work to my parents, sisters for their love, concern, moral and financial support during the period of the studies.

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CHAPTER ONE

1.0 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of the Study

Hands perform the many functions of the human body and are open to a variety of substances which takes account of dust, different body fluids, raw and contaminated materials from the environment and during personal hygiene. (Johnson *et al.*, 2003).

Summelweis (2004) suggested that the hands play an important role in the transmission of infectious agents particularly when people live in close contact with each other. The contagious agents can be spread through hands in families, schools, college dormitories, communities, hospitals and various other settings. In close contact, the infectious agents are not only transferred by hand to hand contact but also indirectly by inanimate objects like doorknobs, sitting ground and so on. (Bloomfield; 2007, and kramer; 2006).

Many studies have linked the hands of individuals (patients, caregivers, and ordinary folks) with the spread of infections in various environments (Knittle *et al.*, 2007; Mortimer *et al.*, 2005; and WHO; 2006). Furthermore, the hands are the most implicated in relation to the transmission of gastrointestinal, respiratory and skin infections. Hand washing and the use of hand sanitizers for hand hygiene are the most important practice to prevent the spread of pathogens (CDC, 2009). Hand washing has been a central component of personal hygiene and a religious and cultural custom for many years. However, the link between handwashing and health was first made less than two centuries ago. (Bloomfield; 2007, and kramer; 2006).

Semmelweis (2006), demonstrated that puerperal fever (also known as childbed fever) was contagious and that this incidence could drastically be reduced by appropriate handwashing by medical caregivers. He made this discovery in 1847 while working in the Maternity Department

of the Vienna Lying-in Hospital. Cleaning hands with antibacterial hand washes stops the spread of microbes or loose transient flora thus preventing infections. (Vineeta, 2014).

After washing hand with liquid hand washes there remain a layer on our skin exterior, this layer protects our normal flora of hands ensuing low rate of different nosocomial infections (Vineeta, 2006). The simple act of washing hands with soap can cut the risk of diarrhoea by more or less half and respiratory tract infections by a third. This makes hand washing a better option for disease prevention than any single vaccine. (Lucet, *et al.*, 2006).

Hands that are apparently soiled or potentially tainted with muck or organic material must be washed with liquid soap and water (Lucet, 2002). The significance of handwashing is more vital when it is allied to health care workers because of possible contagion of bacteria that can be pathogenic or opportunistic. (Yolande and Bressler, 2010).

Studies have revealed that liquid soaps contain antimicrobial active ingredients which take away more bacteria as compared to plain soap (Vineeta; *et al.*, 2006). For control of Staphylococcal infections in hospitals and other health cares, it has been found that the greatest benefits from hand washing came from the first 20% of washing and very petite additional benefits were gained when hand clean-up rate was increased beyond 35%. (Ahmad, *et al.*, 2014).

Washing with plain soap results in more than triple the rate of bacterial infectious diseases transmitted to food as compared to washing with antibacterial hand washes. Comparing hand washes with alcohol-based solutions and washing with antibacterial for a median time of 30 seconds, each one showed that the alcohol-based hand washes reduced bacterial contamination 26% more than the antibacterial. (Ahmad, *et al.*, 2014).

But liquid soap and water is the more effective than alcohol-based hand rubs for reducing HINI influenza a virus and *Clostridium difficile* spores from hands. (Richard, *et al.*, 1999).

Hand sanitizers were invented by Lupe Hernandez, a registered nurse in Bakersfield, California, in 1966. While Hernandez was studying to become a nurse, she learned that cleaning alcohol can be delivered via a gel so that cleaning could occur without a soap and water. (CDC, 2002).

Hand sanitizers are alcohol-containing preparations designed for application to the hands for reducing the number of viable microorganisms on the hands. (CDC, 2002).

They are also used as supplements or alternatives to hand washing with soap and water (Hammond *et al.*, 2000). Various preparations of hand sanitizers are available including the gel, foam and liquid solutions. While alcohol-based hand sanitizers have been demonstrated to be effective against a wide range of Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria, multi-resistant pathogens, fungi and many viruses (Price, 1939; Sakuragi *et al.*; 1995, Kamp *et al.*, 1999), they have also been reported to have very poor activity against bacterial spores, protozoan oocysts and certain non-enveloped (non-lipophilic) virus. (CDC, 2002).

Despite numerous campaigns and expert opinions encouraging the adaptation of hand hygiene, compliance has been low among individuals and healthcare workers. Some of the reasons for non-compliance with hand hygiene agents include; inaccessibility of hand hygiene agents, prioritizing patients need over hand hygiene. (WHO; 2002, Zerre, *et al.*, 2005. and McGuckin, *et al.*, 2009).

A common barrier to convenient hand washing involves scrubbing both hands with soap for about 20seconds, rinsing for another 30seconds and lastly drying. This puts off harried health-workers and ordinary people from regular hand hygiene. It was 'also documented that, despite the evidence and experts opinions supporting hand hygiene, there is low compliance among individuals. Health care workers in developed and developing countries comply with hand hygiene less than 30 of times they should. (Zerr, *et al.*, 2005, McGuckin, *et al.*, 2009).

Some of the identified barriers to hand hygiene compliance include; lack of easy access of hand hygiene at point of care, insufficient time, forgetfulness, skin irritation etc. Hand sanitizers and hand washes have been suggested as one of the ways to overcome this, among other barriers to hand hygiene compliance. (CDC, 2002)

1.2 Statement of Problem

Hospital and community acquired infections constitute a serious public health problem all over the world (Hassan *et al.*, 2012). These infections have considerable impacts on individuals such as prolonged hospitalization, long term disability, increased risk of antimicrobial resistance, huge financial burdens, high costs for patients and their families life and death. (WHO, 2009).

The centre of disease control and prevention (CDC) estimates that approximately 2million people acquire hospital-associated infections each year and that approximately 90,000 of those patients die as a result of their infections. (Zerr *et al.*, 2005).

The CDD, WHO and many experts promote hand hygieneas a single most important measure in the prevention of hospital-associated infections (WHO; 2009, and CDC 2002). Hand washing and the use of hand sanitizers for hand hygiene are the most important practice to prevent the spread of pathogens. (CDC, 2009).

1.3 Justification

The hands play an important role in the transmission of infections in homes, communities and hospitals and in various other settings. Bacteria are deposited on the skin from external sources causing infections which can be spread more rapidly when people live in close contact with each other or indirectly by inanimate objects like door knobs, sitting grounds etc. Cleaning hands with antibacterial hand wash and sanitizers help stop the spread of microbes or loses transient flora of

hands thus preventing infections. This study will help determine the antibacterial effectiveness of hand wash and sanitizers against these agents.

1.4 Aim

This aim of the study is to evaluate the **antibacterial effectiveness of selected hand sanitizers against *Escherichia coli*.**

Objectives

1. To assess the antimicrobial efficacy of alcohol-based hand sanitizers against *Escherichia coli*.
2. To determine the minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) of the test isolates.

1.6 Research Significance

Personal hygiene practices have been identified as an important contributing factor to foodborne outbreaks. In a report of the factors contributing to foodborne disease outbreaks from 1993 to 1997, contaminated hand contact (26% of disease outbreaks), inadequate cleaning of processing or preparation equipment utensils (25% of disease outbreaks), and infection by an asymptomatic carrier (22% of disease outbreaks) were among the most important factors leading to outbreaks (Olsen *et al.*, 2000; United States Federal Food and Drug Administration [FDA], 2000;). The only factor more important than those related to hand contact was allowing foods to remain at room or warm outdoor temperatures for several hours (29% of disease outbreaks).

Hand hygiene is essential in reducing the risks of foodborne illness. Proper hand sanitation is critical during preparation, distribution, and consumption of food, whether in the home or a congregate environment, such as a dining facility (Hedberg *et al.*, 2006). Proper hand washing with soap and water, then drying, is a proven and effective method of hand sanitation (Smith, and Bartleson, 2009).

Hand washing is one of the most efficient and inexpensive procedures for reducing infections and foodborne diseases. Many foodborne diseases and pathogenic micro-organisms are spread by

contaminated hands (World Health Organization, 2009). Reports indicate that the simple act of washing hands with soap and water reduces incidents of diarrhoea from *Shigella* and other causes by up to 35% (Osserian, and Schlein, 2001).

Hands are the primary mode of transmission for many infectious diseases, particularly among military personnel. Hand hygiene is a proven infection control measure in the military setting (Mott *et al.*, 2007).

According to the CDC (2009), simple hand washing is one of the most effective methods to prevent the spread of infectious diseases. Numerous studies have indicated a strong and consistent association between personal hand hygiene and reduced gastrointestinal disease, respiratory illness, and absenteeism among working personnel (Sandora *et al.*, 2005). The acute respiratory disease has become a major concern for military personnel (Kolavic *et al.*, 2002).

Even though hand hygiene is one of the primary methods used to reduce the faecal-oral transmission of infectious agents, conflicting hand hygiene recommendations often cause confusion among individuals as to what products should be used or what is the best practice to follow for hand washing and hand hygiene.

Hand sanitizers have proven to be useful in decreasing the transmission of some resistant microorganisms and preventing cross-transmission of bacteria from person-to-person (Antoniak, 2004). Even with the institution of alcohol-based sanitizers, compliance with hand hygiene remains problematic. Therefore, this study is relevant as it aims to measure the efficiencies of some selected hand sanitizers against some bacterial strains.

1.7 Scope of the Study

Conceptually the study hovers around the antibacterial effectiveness of Hand sanitizer. Extensive investigation is conducted on Hand sanitizer antibacterial properties, medicinal use and its effect on bacteria

CHAPTER TWO

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Introduction

Hand washing has been a central component of personal hygiene *and* a religious *and* cultural custom for years. However, the link between Hand washing *and* health was first made less than two centuries ago (Vineeta, 2006). Semele's was the first to demonstrate that puerperal fever (also known as childhood fever) was contagious *and* that this incidence could drastically be reduced by appropriate Hand washing by medical caregivers. He made this discovery in 1847 while working in the Maternity Department of Vienna Lying-in Hospital. (Vineeta, 2006). Cleaning Hands with antibacterial Hand washes stops the spread of microbes or loses transient flora thus preventing infections (Vineeta, 2006). After washing Hands with liquid Hand washes, there remains a layer on our skin exterior, this layer protects our normal flora of Hands ensuring a low rate of different nosocomial infections (Vineeta, 2006).

The emergence of novel pathogens, bacterial or viral, has always posed serious challenges to public health around the globe. One of these dangerous pathogens is "severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2" or SARS-CoV-2, more commonly known for causing coronavirus disease 2019 or COVID-19, which has been declared a global *pandemic* by the World Health Organization in early 2020. Since its discovery in December 2019 in Wuhan, there have been over three million confirmed cases worldwide by April 2020. (Sakuragi *et al.*, 2005).

With cases increasing exponentially around the world, it has caused significant burden on all aspects of society despite aggressive isolation methods to prevent the spread of the virus. Currently, therapeutic strategies to deal with COVID-19 are only supportive, making prevention aimed at reducing transmission the best method at this time.

One of the many ways implemented to prevent the spread of this virus, as with previous contagious pathogens, is frequent *and* effective Hand washing. In both healthcare *and* community settings, alcohol-based Hand sanitizers have become a popular alternative to the traditional Hand washing with soap *and* water. Alcohol-based Hand sanitizers have been utilized as an effective alternative to Hand washing to prevent the spread of bacterial *and* viral infections, making it one of the essential protocols in decreasing healthcare burden. (Sakuragi *et al.*, 2005).

A range of Hand sanitizers are available with various combinations of ingredients *and* modes of delivery. Given the popularity of Hand sanitizers during this *pandemic*, it is important to *understand* which types of Hand sanitizers work best against this novel virus. In this review, we will discuss the role of various types of alcohol-based Hand sanitizers in effective elimination of bacterial *and* viral pathogens with the focus on the effectiveness against enveloped viruses, such as SARS-CoV-2 (Sakuragi *et al.*, 2005).

Hand sanitizers were invented by Lupe Hernandez, a registered nurse in Bakersfield, California, in 1966. While Hernandez was studying to become a nurse, she learned that cleaning alcohol can be delivered via a gel so that cleaning could occur without soap *and* water. (Vineeta, 2006).

Hand sanitizers have been demonstrated to be effective against a wide range of Gram-positive *and* Gram-negative bacteria, multi-resistant pathogens, fungi *and* many viruses (Sakuragi *et al.*, 2005, Kampf *et al.*, 2009).

The review of the literature is crucial in any research work. This is because it enables the researcher to study different theories related to the identified topic *and* gain clarity of the research topic (Katsikeas *and* Leorned, 1996). In this chapter, a detailed literature review on Hand sanitizer, its components, properties, use *and* application is provided.

2.2 Hand Sanitizers

Hand sanitizers also called Hand antiseptics, Hand rub, or Hand rub, are agents applied to the Hands to remove common pathogens (disease-causing organisms). Hand sanitizer comes in foams, gel or liquid form. (Ewen, 2011 *and* David, 2015). Hand sanitizers are either alcohol-based or non-alcohol based. The majority of alcohol-based Hand antiseptics contain either isopropanol, ethanol, n-propanol, or a combination of two of these products. Because of the drying nature of alcohol *and* glycerol, skin softening agents are also added to the solution (Okè, *et al.*, 2013). Hand sanitizers are not appropriate for use when Hands are visibly dirty or contaminated with proteinaceous materials. Utilizing Hand sanitizers appropriately can reduce the load of micro-organisms on the Hand *and* have been researched to minimize cross-infection (Ahmad, *et al.*, 2014).

Alcohol-based Hand sanitizers, or alcohol-based Hand rubs (ABHRs), are instant Hand hygiene products; the antimicrobial activity of which is due to the ability of alcohol to denature the protein. Alcohol-based sanitizers have been demonstrated to be effective on both Gram-positive *and* Gram-negative bacteria *and* multi-resistant pathogens (Price, 1939, Sakaragi, *et al.*, 1995, *and* Kampf, 1999). These products usually contain a quantity of alcohol varying from 60% to 95%, *and* a thickening agent or humectants such as polyacrylic acid, glycerin, or propylene glycol to decrease the drying effect of alcohol. ABHRs have documented microbiological activity against bacteria (Fendler *et al.*, 2002 *and* Rotter 1996), fungi *and* some enveloped viruses including HIV, herpes, adenovirus, influenza *and* parainfluenza viruses (Fendler *and* Groziak 2002).

Finally, another group of instant Hand products known as alcohol-free Hand sanitizers, such as povidone-iodine-, triclosan or quaternary ammonium-based compounds, has also attracted growing interest over recent years. Despite being historically recognized as less effective than ABHRs, more recent formulations prepared with benzalkonium chloride (BZK) have

demonstrated many advantages over ABHR including residual antimicrobial activity after use, less drying effect on Hand skin, *and* lack of decrease in efficacy after repeated use (Dyier, *et al.*, 1998). The use of waterless Hand sanitizers as an alternative to conventional Hand washing has long been debated. Despite some potential advantages over conventional water *and* soap (quicker *and* easier usage), instant Hand products are generally considered to more effectively meet needs in hospital *and* healthcare, rather than food preparation, settings. ABHRs containing 60% to 95% alcohol are recommended as an alternative to Hand washing in hospital *and* health-care settings when Hands are not visibly soiled (CDC, 2002).

Antimicrobial products (i.e. Hand washes *and* sanitizers) whether used by consumers in the home or medical personnel in the hospital, reduce or eliminate bacteria that can lead to skin infections, intestinal illness or other commonly transmitted diseases (Brian; 2006). Additionally, these products are essential for the following;

Individuals who are in close physical contact with people at high risk for infection, such as the elderly-cared for in retirement facilities or the immune-suppressed.

Individuals who are in contact with an organism are likely to be transmitted by direct contact, such as diarrhoea, upper respiratory infections *and* skin infections.

Individuals who are in settings in which infectious disease transmission is likely, such as in food preparations, chronic-care residences, prisons, child-care centres *and* preschools.

For millions of Americans, these situations are normal occurrences, further show casting the role antimicrobial products play in everyday life (Brian, 2006). The main benefit of Hand washing *and* the use of Hand sanitizers are to; Remove or destroy potentially harmful micro-organisms, prevent the Hands from becoming a vector of cross-infection, render the Hands socially clean in order to continue the delivery of health care thereby resulting in less risk of diseases. (CDC, 2002).

2.3 Hand Sanitizer History

Hand sanitizer is commonly used as a generalized or synonym term for Hand antisepsis, which often refers to the application or use of Hand rubs, gels, foams, or pre-moistened towelettes (or Hand wipes) that use various chemicals as active ingredients (Larson, 1995). In 1966, Lupe Hernandez discovered that alcohol could be delivered via a gel for the purpose of sanitizing whenever soap *and* water were not available, or there was limited time for Hand washing (Anonymous, 2012). After GOJO launched Purell as the first commercial Hand sanitizer in the late 1990s, even Hernandez could not have envisaged the explosion of the popularity in Hand sanitizers. One industry report noted that in the United States (U.S.) market alone, the growth of Hand sanitizers is overwhelming, valued at \$28 million in 2002, *and* \$80 million by 2006. It is predicted to be worth more than \$402 million by 2015 (Deep Research Reports, 2014).

In the past few years, Hand sanitizers have become increasingly common in the U.S., *and* most particularly among younger parents. Global threats such as Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome (SARS), Avian Flu, *and* the more recent H7N9 Swine Flu or Ebola have led to a surge in demand for Hand sanitizers (Frieden, Damon, Bell, Kenyon, *and* Nichol, 2014). Once considered a fad for only those concerned with germ control *and* bacteria contamination, Hand sanitizers are now commonly found in hospitals, care homes, government buildings, restaurants, supermarkets, *and* public restrooms (Jarvis, 1996). The use of alcohol-based Hand sanitizers can be considered as either a supplement to traditional Hand washing or as a primary means of Hand hygiene (Boyce *and* Pittet, 2002). These recommendations are based on well-designed experimental, clinical, *and* epidemiologic studies (Dyer *et al.*, 2000; Dyer, Gerenratch, *and* Wadhams, 1998; Guinan *et al.*, 2002; Lee *et al.*, 2005; Storr *and* Clayton, 2004; White *et al.*, 2001; White *et al.*, 2005).

Various studies (Muto, Sistrom, *and* Farr, 2000; Larson, Gomez, Lee, Della, Kain, *and* Keswick, 2003; Liu *et al.*, 2010) have questioned the effectiveness of alcohol-based hand antisepsis (e.g. sanitizers, foams, *and* wipers) compared to traditional soap-water Hand washing. Larson *et al.* (2003) conducted a longitude study of 224 primary caretakers in households in northern Manhattan, New York to compare the difference between those who washed their hands with soap *and* water *and* those who used a commercial antimicrobial product. The researchers found no significant differences in the mean bacterial log counts either before or after Hand washing between homemakers using the antimicrobial product or plain soap at baseline or after a year of use (all p-values > 0.28).

Other studies have shown the benefits of effective Hand sanitation including reducing the spread of diarrhoea *and* gastrointestinal illnesses by almost 50% (Hilburn *et al.*, 2003; Sandora *et al.*, 2005). Commercial Hand sanitizers, which generally contain 60% to 70% ethanol or isopropanol, are one of the most effective agents for reducing the number of viable pathogens on the Hands even with artificial fingernails (Guilhermetti, Hernandez, Fukushigue, Garcia, *and* Cardoso, 2001; McNeil, Foster, Hedderwick, *and* Kauffman, 2001; Rotter, 1999). Some researchers who recommend Hand sanitizers over soap-water Hand washing have pointed out that soap-water Hand washing fails to remove biotic or living organisms, *and* the possibility exists for soap contamination (Cardoso, Pereiraa, Zequimb, *and* Guilhermettia, 1999).

Other researchers have concluded that soap-water Hand washing is less efficient than Hand sanitizers (Johnson, *et al.*, 2005; Michaels, Gangar, Lin, *and* Doyle, 2003; Widmer, 2000). In 2002, the CDC revised their *Guidelines for Hand Hygiene in Health Care Settings* *and* stated that alcohol-based Hand sanitizers are more effective for *standard* Hand washing or Hand antisepsis by healthcare workers than soap or antimicrobial soaps (Ayliffe, Babb, Davies, *and* Lilly, 1988;

Boyce *and* Pittet, 2002; Cardoso, Pereira, Zequimb, *and* Guilhermettia, 1999; Larson, 1986; Ojarvi, 1980; Paulson, Fendler, Dolan, *and* Williams, 1999; Rotter *and* Koller, 1992; Zaragoza, Salles, Gomez, Bayas, *and* Trilla, 1999).

Studies have also demonstrated the effectiveness of instant Hand sanitizers in reducing illness (White *et al.*, 2005). The CDC (2002) has recommended that using alcohol-based Hand sanitizers is acceptable if Hands are not visibly soiled (Boyce *and* Pittet, 2002). The use of alcohol-based Hand sanitizers, which are efficient against a variety of bacteria *and* viruses, can be considered as either a supplement to traditional Hand washing or as a primary means of Hand hygiene. These recommendations are based on well-designed experimental, clinical, *and* epidemiologic studies (White *et al.*, 2005).

Among the variety of bacteria *and* viruses encountered every day, human noroviruses are the most common (Hall *et al.*, 2014). Nor virus is the leading cause of acute gastroenteritis *and* foodborne disease in the U.S., causing one in every fifteen Americans to become ill each year, resulting in 56,000 to 71,000 hospitalizations *and* 570 to 800 deaths (Hall *et al.*, 2014).

Cannon, Aydin, Mann, Bolton, Zhao, *and* Doyle (2012) evaluated a sanitizer of levulinic acid plus the anionic detergent sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS) against noroviruses. Due to the inability to custom human noroviruses in the laboratory, surrogate viruses such as murine norovirus *and* feline calicivirus were used. The combination of 0.5% levulinic acid plus 0.5% SDS inactivated both surrogates by 3 to 4.21 log after one minute of exposure. Similarly, murine norovirus inoculated onto stainless steel was reduced by > 1.50 log after one minute *and* by > 3.3 log PFU/ml after five minutes of exposure to a liquid or foaming solution of 5% levulinic acid plus 2% SDS. The presence of levulinic acid (up to 10%) in the virus inoculum did not significantly reduce sanitizer

efficacy. The results of this study indicate the potential uses of levulinic acid plus SDS as a sanitizer in a variety of settings to reduce human norovirus (Cannon *et al.*, 2012).

Another study tested the efficacy of a Hand sanitizer on *Escherichia coli* (*E. coli*) from different food sources in a food service establishment. The results showed a Hand sanitizer containing 70% ethanol achieved a 5.22-log reduction in *E. coli* while a non-antimicrobial soap water washing method resulted in only 3.10-log reduction. When Hands were heavily soiled from Handling *E. coli* inoculated ground beef, a similar effect persisted, with a 4.60-log and 4.11 log reduction using a Hand sanitizer and a soap-water method, respectively. This suggests that although the process of Hand washing helped to remove pathogens from Hands, the use of a Hand sanitizer regimen was also effective for reducing organisms (Edmonds *et al.*, 2012). Therefore, the authors suggest the use of a well-formulated alcohol based Hand rub as part of a Hand-washing regimen to reduce the risk of infection and transmission in food service facilities.

Park, Barclay, Macinga, Charbonneau, Pettigrew, and Vinje (2010) evaluated the virucidal efficacy of seven commercial Hand sanitizers containing various active ingredients, such as Ethanol, Triclosan, and Chlorhexidine. They then compared their effectiveness against mouse norovirus and feline calicivirus. Based on the outcomes of a quantitative suspension test, only one triclosan-based product (0.1% triclosan, pH 3.0) and one ethanol-based product (72% ethanol, pH 2.9) moderately reduced the infectivity of both mouse norovirus and feline calicivirus (by ≥ 3.4 and > 2.6 log units, respectively) (Park *et al.*, 2010).

The other four commercial Hand sanitizers reduced the infectivity of both mouse norovirus and feline calicivirus only after five minutes of exposure. Ethanol and isopropanol concentrations $\geq 70\%$ reduced the infectivity of mouse norovirus by ≥ 2.6 log units, whereas 50 and 70% ethanol reduced the infectivity of feline calicivirus by ≥ 2.2 log units after exposure for five minutes. A

significant reduction in both human noroviruses after exposure to ethanol or isopropanol indicates that both alcohols are effective.

It is clear that most of the essential ingredients contained within commercial Hand sanitizers are effective against human noroviruses (Park *et al.*, 2010). While these data supported the use of Hand sanitizers, similar efficacy tests utilizing a 15-second exposure kill test, found that alcohol-based Hand sanitizers are effective against a broad spectrum of bacteria, including antibiotic resistant species, fungi, *and* other viruses (Table 2.1, 2.2 *and* 2.3).

2.4 Hand Sanitizer Ingredients

There are 2 large categories of Hand sanitizers: (1) non-alcohol-based Hand sanitizers (NABHS) *and* (2) alcohol-based Hand sanitizers (ABHS). The most common primary active ingredient of NABHS, benzalkonium chloride, a quaternary ammonium, is a commonly used disinfectant. (CDC, 2002).

Disinfectants with benzalkonium chloride are generally less irritating than those with alcohol, though more recent evidence suggests it may cause contact dermatitis more often than previously thought. Although ABHS are less user-friendly on skin than NABHS, ABHS predominate in health care settings given their low cost *and* efficacy of reducing infectious transmission. NABHS, however, are less worrisome regarding their flammability *and* abuse potential. (CDC, 2002).

Hand sanitizer preparations containing alcohol on the other Hand can include ethanol, isopropyl alcohol, *n*-propanol, or a combination of these, water, as well as excipients *and* humectants. Solutions containing alcohols between 60% *and* 95% in volume are most prevalent *and* effective. Humectants are included to prevent skin dehydration *and* excipients help stabilize the product as well as prolong the time needed for the evaporation of alcohol, thereby increasing its biocidal activity. (CDC, 2002).

2.5 Efficacy of Hand Sanitizers on Bacteria, Fungi and Viruses

2.5.1 Bacteria and fungi

Traditionally, bacteria on Hands can be categorized as resident *and* transient floras. Common resident floras include *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Staphylococcus epidermidis*, *and Enterococcus faecalis*, which colonize deep layers of the skin *and* are resistant to mechanical removal. On the other hand, transient floras such as *S. aureus*, *Escherichia coli*, *and Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, colonize the superficial layers of skin. (Hall *et al.*, 2014).

There are also numerous bacterial strains that can be transmitted to the host from other sources that can potentially develop into a variety of bacterial infections. ABHS are very effective for quickly destroying many pathogens by the action of the aqueous alcohol solution without the need for water or drying with towels. According to the Centers for Disease Control *and* Prevention (CDC), ABHS have excellent *in vitro* antimicrobial activity, including multidrug-resistant pathogens, such as methicillin-resistant *S. aureus*, vancomycin-resistant *Enterococcus*. (Hall *et al.*, 2014).

Specific *in vitro* studies show that Hand sanitizers containing 60%-80% ethanol produced 4 to 6 log reduction in 15-30 seconds against a range of bacterial *and* fungal species. Numerous studies have also documented *in vivo* antimicrobial activity from contaminated Hands. While different alcohol-based Hand sanitizers all demonstrated antimicrobial effects against various gram-positive *and* gram-negative bacteria using the Kirby-Bauer method, which uses antibiotic-impregnated disks to test the susceptibility of strains, propanol-based sanitizers were more effective compared to ethanol with the greatest zone of inhibition. (Fricker, 2012).

With increasing use of Hand sanitizers as an infectious control measure, it is also important to note any potential tolerance mechanisms from bacteria. An *in vitro* alcohol tolerance assay using a

lower concentration of isopropanol showed that newer isolates of *E. faecium* were more alcohol-tolerant than their predecessors. Other similar studies on other pathogens have also demonstrated increasing tolerance when exposed to lower concentrations of alcohol. Tolerance is not only limited to alcohol, but also exists for BC. (Fricker, 2012).

The presence of any selective pressure in environments encourage microbes to adapt *and* evolve resistance to such pressures, *and* in the case of BC, researchers have observed resistant strains that were able to survive certain concentrations of BC (0.1%-0.4%) since the 1960s. Given this, tolerance to quaternary ammonium compounds is not a novel observation. As time goes on *and* the use of both alcohol *and* BC continue in Hand sanitizers *and* disinfectants, it is inevitable that tolerance will only increase. While future studies are conducted to determine novel mechanisms of tolerance, it is essential to emphasize adherence to Hand hygiene protocols that require adequate exposure, volume, *and* concentrations of Hand sanitizers to minimize selective pressures *and* thus tolerance. (Fricker, 2012).

2.5.2 Viruses

Although viruses are more difficult to directly study *in vivo* compared to bacteria, numerous studies have attempted to validate the effectiveness of Hand sanitizers on viruses. The World Health Organization recommends alcohol-based Hand sanitizer formulations against bovine viral diarrhoea virus, hepatitis C virus, Zika virus, murine norovirus, *and* coronaviruses as shown with effective inactivation in quantitative suspension tests. Other formulations from Sterillium that contain isopropanol as the main ingredient also completely inactivated enveloped enteric *and* respiratory viruses, such as H1N1 influenza A virus, but failed to inactivate non-enveloped viruses, except rotavirus. A number of *in vivo* studies have also been conducted where the virus is applied

to fingertips *and* the efficacy of the Hand sanitizers in reducing the numbers of viral particles recoverable from Hands is determined. (Edmonds *et al.*, 2012).

Many of these finger pad tests show moderate efficacy against most nonenveloped viral strains, which are known to be more resistant to disinfectants than enveloped viruses. It is crucial to keep note of the type of viral strains as high concentrations of ethanol has shown to be highly effective against enveloped viruses *and* thus is effective against the majority of clinically relevant viruses. That being said, although nonenveloped viruses such as Hepatitis A *and* enteroviruses require 70%-80% alcohol to be reliably inactivated, Sattar et al (2012) suggest that 60% ethanol was sufficient to reduce the titers of rotavirus, adenovirus, *and* rhinovirus by $>3 \log_{10}$ within a 10-second contact period. Even with nonenveloped viruses, satisfactory activity can be achieved with higher alcohol concentrations *and* extended contact times. (Macinga, *and* Fricker, 2012).

As evidence on the novel SARS-CoV-2 continues to rapidly emerge, data from previous coronaviruses can be extrapolated in the context of the efficacy of Hand disinfection given their structural similarity. A systematic review examining the 2002-04 SARS outbreak indicated that 9 out of 10 small case-control studies pointed towards the idea that Hand washing decreases the likelihood of nosocomial *and* community transmission, although only three showed statistical significance, partly explained due to the small sample sizes of the studies. A portion of the studies varied in the specific method of Hand washing; some studies used Hand sanitizers, while others did not specify whether it was achieved through soap *and* water or sanitizers. Although direct in vivo confirmation of virus inactivation after Hand sanitizer use is infeasible to achieve in a *standardized* method, in vitro studies have confirmed that alcohol-based Hand sanitizers can be effective in decreasing the viral load. Specifically, in vitro studies using sputum cultures of SARS-

CoV infected patients with four different alcohol-based Hand sanitizer formulations were all able to inactivate the virus below the limit of detection. (CDC, 2002).

Transmissions of SARS-CoV-2 have been described with incubation times of up to 10 days, facilitating its spread via droplets, contaminated Hands, or surfaces. As such, it is important to note the efficacy of inactivating viruses on all modes of transmission. Alcohol-based disinfectants have also been shown to effectively inactivate SARS-CoV *and* MERS-CoV (Middle East respiratory syndrome-related coronavirus) on inanimate surfaces, such as metal, glass, *and* plastic. (CDC, 2002).

One of the key limitations for analyzing the true efficacy of Hand disinfection arises from the method of data collection via retrospective self-reporting, which can lack *standardization and* objectivity in frequency *and* method of Hand washing. There is also a myriad of confounding variables, especially in hospital settings, such as frequency *and* extent of contact with infected persons *and* the use of personal protective equipment. As Hand hygiene is one aspect of a multicomponent intervention to reduce infection rates, it is difficult to truly assess the effectiveness of Hand sanitizers independently.

Table 2.2.1 In-Vitro Antimicrobial Efficacy of Alcohol Gel Hand Sanitizer on Challenge

Bacteria

Challenge Bacteria	Reduction Percent	Reduction Log10
<i>Bacillus megaterium</i>	> 99.998	> 4.68
<i>Clostridium difficile</i>	> 99.998	> 4.75
<i>Corynebacterium diphtheria</i>	> 99.999	> 5.00
<i>Enterococcus faecalis</i>	> 99.999	> 5.00
<i>Enterococcus faecium</i>	> 99.999	> 5.00
<i>Lactobacillus plantarum</i>	> 99.999	> 5.00
<i>Listeria monocytogenes</i>	> 99.999	> 5.00
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	> 99.999	> 5.00
<i>Staphylococcus epidermidis</i>	> 99.999	> 5.00
<i>Streptococcus pneumonia</i>	> 99.994	> 4.20
<i>Streptococcus pyogenes</i>	> 99.999	> 5.00
<i>Acinetobacter baumannii</i>	> 99.999	> 5.00
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	> 99.999	> 5.00
<i>Citrobacter freundii</i>	> 99.999	> 5.00
<i>Enterobacter aero genes</i>	> 99.999	> 5.00
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	> 99.999	> 5.00
<i>Escherichia coli (O157:H7)</i>	> 99.999	> 5.00
<i>Klebsiella ozaenae</i>	> 99.999	> 5.00
<i>Klebsiella pneumonia</i>	> 99.999	> 5.00
<i>Proteus mirabilis</i>	> 99.999	> 5.00
<i>Proteus vulgaris</i>	> 99.999	> 5.00
<i>Salmonella enteritidis</i>	> 99.999	> 5.00
<i>Salmonella typhimurium</i>	> 99.999	> 5.00
<i>Serratia marcescens</i>	> 99.999	> 5.00
<i>Shigella dysenteriae</i>	> 99.999	> 5.00
<i>Shigella sonnei</i>	> 99.999	> 5.00

Table 2.2.2 In-Vitro Antimicrobial Efficacy of Alcohol Gel Hand Sanitizer on Challenge Fungi

Challenge fungi	Reduction	Reduction
	Percent	Log10
<i>Aspergillus flavus</i>	> 99.999	> 5.00
<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	> 99.998	> 4.72
<i>Candida albicans</i>	> 99.999	> 5.00
<i>Candida tropicalis</i>	> 99.999	> 5.00
<i>Epidermophyton floccosum</i>	> 99.988	> 3.92
<i>Penicillium citrinum</i>	> 99.999	> 5.00
<i>Trichophyton mentagrophytes</i>	> 99.999	> 5.00

Table 2.2.3 In-Vitro Antimicrobial Efficacy of Alcohol Gel Hand Sanitizer on Challenge Virus

Challenge Bacteria	Reduction	Reduction
	Percent	Log10
Herpes simplex virus type 1	≥ 99.999	≥ 5.00
HIV type 1	≥ 99.993	≥ 4.14
Influenza virus type A2	≥ 99.999	≥ 5.25
Parainfluenza virus type 2	≥ 99.996	≥ 4.39
Parainfluenza virus type 3	≥ 99.993	≥ 4.14
Rhinovirus type 16	≥ 99.994	≥ 4.25
Herpes simplex virus type 1	≥ 99.999	≥ 5.00

Note. Adapted from “The impact of alcohol Hand sanitizer use on infection rates in an extended care facility”, by Fendler, E. J., Ali, Y., Hammond, B. S., Lyons, M. K., Kelley, M. B., and Vowell, N. A. (2002). The impact of alcohol Hand sanitizer use on infection rates in an extended care facility. *American journal of infection control*, 30(4), 226-233.

2.6 Types of Hand Sanitizers and Hand Washes

Depending on the active ingredients used, Hand sanitizers can be classified as one of two types: alcohol-based or alcohol-free. Alcohol-based products typically contain between 60 and 95% alcohol, usually in the form of ethanol, isopropanol, and n-propanol (Todd *et al.*, 2011). At those concentrations alcohol immediately denatures proteins, effectively neutralizing certain types of microorganisms, (Raymond; 2015). Alcohol-free products are generally based on disinfectants, such as Benzalkonium chloride (BAC), or antimicrobial agents, such as Triclosan (Raymond, 2015). The activity of disinfectants and antimicrobial agents are both immediate and persistent (Anoosh, 2015). Many Hand sanitizers also contain emollients (e.g., glycerin) that soothe the skin, thickening agents, and fragrance (Ewen, 2011 and David, 2015). Antimicrobial wash products include Hand washes/soaps and body washes.

2.7 Compositions of Hand Washes and Hand Sanitizers

Within all antiseptic products, there is an active chemical agent (called a biocide) responsible for the destruction of microorganisms. These active ingredients include alcohol, iodine, triclosan, chlorohexidine gluconate, benzalkonium chloride, benzethonium chloride, triclocarban, and benzethonium chloride, para-chloro-meta-xyleneol, triclocarban, and triclosan (NDAC, 2005). Leave-on Hand-washes contain alcohol, benzalkonium chloride, and benzethonium chloride. Yet, although all of these biocides may be used by manufacturers, only two active ingredients have been recognized as safe and effective by the TFM. These active ingredients are 60-95% alcohol

and 5-10% providone-iodine (NDAC, 2005). Hand washes and Hand sanitizer are made up of chemical agents, which have antimicrobial, softening, cleansing, thickening properties. And they are divided into 2 types; active and inactive ingredients. Active ingredients have antimicrobial activity while inactive ingredients may serve as surfactants detergent, humectant, preservative, fragrance etc. (Okè *et al.*, 2013). Active ingredients of sanitizers include isopropanol, ethanol, n-propanol or providing iodine while the inactive ingredients usually include a thickening agent (such as polyacrylic acid for gels), humectants (such as glycerin for liquid, rubs) or propylene glycol and essential oil of plants (Ahmad, *et al.*, 2014). Alcohol-based products; these products vary greatly in composition range from 54% isopropanol to 70% ethanol (Harvey, 1992). The choice of this type of rinse-free antimicrobial product often is subjected and mainly based on factors such as cost, presence of emollients in the formula, fragrances, delivery vehicle (e.g., gel, foam) size and marketing. Selection is less often based on the effectiveness of the product at eliminating bacteria after a single application.

2.7 Application of Hand Sanitizers in Congregate Settings

Hand hygiene has been cited to be one of the significant methods for preventing communicable diseases (Boyce and Pittet, 2002). Studies link Hand hygiene to disease and infections in many congregate settings, including elementary schools, college and university campuses, healthcare, and military (Ryan *et al.*, 2001).

There has been a significant amount of research conducted on infection control and diseases within the elementary school environment using Hand sanitizers (Dyer *et al.*, 2000). In 2000, one study compared students using Clean Hands Hand sanitizers with a control group of students using normal Hand washing with soap and water. The study found 41.9% fewer illness-related absence days, representing a 28.9% and a 49.7% decrease in gastrointestinal- and respiratory-related

illnesses, respectively. Likewise, absences decreased by 31.7% overall, consisting of a 44.2% reduction in gastrointestinal-related illnesses *and* 50.2% decrease in respiratory-related illnesses (Dyer *et al.*, 2000). In 2002, another study was conducted with 16 individual schools, including more than 6,000 students in Delaware, Ohio, California, *and* Tennessee. Different schools from each district were paired into experimental *and* control groups. Alcohol-based Hand sanitizers were used by the students *and* staff when entering *and* leaving the classroom in the experimental group, *and* absenteeism due to infection was recorded for both groups. A 19.8% reduction in absenteeism for the experimental group was achieved ($p < .05$). Data with the largest teacher population ($N = 246$) in the experimental group showed that teacher absenteeism also decreased 10.1% (Dolan, *and* Sandra, 2000).

Other experiments conducted within the elementary school setting included educational *and* promotional campaigns concerning Hand sanitizer use. One study in Pennsylvania included 290 students from five independent schools with classrooms divided into experimental *and* control groups. The students in the experimental groups went through an educational program, which included a formal lecture, videos, *and* pamphlets. After the data were collected for three months, a 50.6% reduction in absences in the experimental group was noted ($p < .001$) (McGuckin, *and* Ali, 2002).

Similar studies have been conducted among college students. A confidential, self-administered online survey included a total of 994 college students, including 49% undergraduates *and* 30% graduate students, of which 34% lived in residence halls.

Approximately 34% of respondents who lived on campus ($N = 339$) reported that their residence hall did not provide soap. The top five reasons reported for not washing were: forgetting (63%), too busy (52%), unnecessary (37%), soap was not in a convenient location (31%), *and* no soap

was available (26%). Approximately 70% of all respondents indicated that they would use a Hand sanitizer instead of Hand washing if it was available on the campus *and* 42% indicated that they would use it on the residential campus. The authors recommended the implementation of Hand sanitizers on campus to further improve Hand hygiene compliance *and* reduce the rates of infection *and* absenteeism (Scott *and* Vanick, 2007).

CHAPTER THREE

3.0 Materials and Methods

Regarding the protection of community and health professionals suffering from a COVID-19 outbreak, currently, different alcohol-based hand sanitizers have been distributed. Even though for effective protection effective alcohol-based hand sanitizers are mandatory. Their efficacy was not evaluated. This is the reason why this research was designed to assess the antimicrobial efficacy of alcohol-based hand sanitizers against *Escherichia coli*.

This chapter presents the methodological aspects of the study. It presents the study design, test materials, test organism, quality control, ethical consideration, media preparation, data analysis among others.

3.1 Study Design

The study was an experimental, laboratory-based study, which was carried out at the Biology Department of Umaru Musa Yar'adua University Kasina, Katsina state, Nigeria.

3.2 Test Materials

The test materials include; Petri dish, Muelle Hinton agar, syringe, plain container, hand gloves, distilled water, normal saline, test tubes, pipette tips (100 -1000 μ l) and timer.

3.3 Test Organisms

Sanitizers containing an alcohol concentration between 60–85% are suggested to kill 99.99% of microorganisms on hands. The sanitizers which are effective on bacteria are effective in virus and vice versa. Therefore, we were forced to assess the efficacy of alcohol-based hand sanitizers only on selected bacteria, but not on virus (SARS-CoV-2) due to our laboratory set up constraint for viral isolation and growth.

Following this assumption and reviewing related literature *Escherichia coli*, was selected at the laboratory of the Biology Department, Umaru Musa Yar'adua University Katsina. The microorganism was isolated from clinical specimens. During the study, clinical specimens were inoculated on Mueller Hinton agar. The isolated test organism was stored on storage media and kept at 2–8° C. It were refreshed on nutrient agar and used when needed.

3.4 Hand Sanitizers used in the study and their composition

Four hand sanitizer products of alcohol-based hand sanitizers were purchased from local vendors at Central Market of Katsina, Katsina state. However, the research avoids tear or not sealed, expired and unlabelled (unknown manufacturer) hand sanitizers. The hand sanitizers were safely transported to biological science laboratory of Umaru Musa Yar'adua University, Katsina for further experimental analysis. Below are the hand sanitizer used for the study and their composition;

3.4.1 Instant Hand Sanitizer,

Ingredients; Ethyl alcohol 70% v/v Water, glycerin, propylene glycol, acrylates/c10-30 alkyl acrylate crosspolymer, isopropyl alcohol, aminomethyl propanol, isopropyl myristate, caprylyl glycol, phenoxyethanol, fragrance, tocopheryl acetate.

3.4.2 Liberate Hand Gel

Ingredients; Aqua, Sodium Cocoyl Glycinate, Cocamidopropyl Hydroxysultaine, Lauroyl Methyl Glucamide, Sodium Lauroyl Isethionate, Glycerin, Glycol Distearate, Dehydroacetic Acid, Benzyl Alcohol, Benzoic Acid, Hydroxypropyl Methylcellulose, Fragrance, Hydrolyzed Jojoba Esters, Oryza Sativa (Rice) Bran Extract, Rosmarinus Officinalis (Rosemary) Leaf Extract, Helianthus Annuus (Sunflower) Extract, Tocopherol, Sativa Seed Oil, Salix Nigra (Willow) Bark Extract, C12-13 Alkyl Lactate, Disodium Edta, Charcoal Powder, Citric Acid.

3.4.3 Drug Field Hand Sanitizer

Ingredients; 62% Isopropyl Alcohol, water, glycerin, propylene glycol, fragrance, triethanolamine, carbopol 940, acetate isopropyl myristate.

3.4.4 Cussons Carex.

Ingredients; Aqua, sodium Laureth sulfate, lauramidopropyl betaine, glycerine, laureth-4, parfum, sodium chloride, sodium lactate, cocamidopropyl PG-dimonium chloride phosphate, polyquaternium-39, citric acid, hexylene glycol, sodium citrate, sodium benzoate, tetrasodium EDTA, methyldibromo glutaronitrile, phenoxyethanol, methylparaben, propylparaben, sodium benzotriazolyl butylphenol sulfate, buteth-3, tributyl citrate, citronellol, butylphenyl methylpropional, linalool, alpha isomethyl ionone, hexyl cinnamal, limonene, CI 42051.

3.5 Sample Preparation and Serial Dilution

2mls of the Hand sanitizers was measured and used for serial dilution . This gave a stock solution which contained a concentration of 100%. The solution was then transferred into a test tube and mixed well by using syringe. Three dilutions were additionally made from each of the hand sanitizer's as 50%, 25%, and 12.5% respectively (Otokunefor and Dappa,2017)

3.6 Preparation of Mueller Hinton Agar Plate

(3.9) grams of Mueller Hinton agar powder were weighed. The MHA powder was dissolved in 100ml of distilled water in 1000ml conical flask. Magnetic stirrer was used to stir the mixture to ensure proper mixing. After stirring, nutrient agar solution was autoclaved for sterilization at temperature of 121°C for 15 minutes. After autoclave, the hot sterilized nutrient agar solution was poured into the Petri plates in the laminar air flow cabinet. Each of the Petri-plates contained approximately 25ml of nutrient agar solution which can only occupy 60-70% of the Petri plate.

The nutrient agar plates were allowed to solidify in the cabinet and the UV of the laminar air flow cabinet was on for 15 minutes to achieve sterilization (Magaldi *et al.*, 2004).

3.7 Preparation of the Disk and Impregnation

From the four different concentrations of complexes which were 100%, 50%, 25% and 12.5%. Sterile disk punched using Whatmann No 2 filter paper were impregnated into each of the respective tubes allowed to soak for 30 minutes and dispensed in each of the already seeded plates of *Escherichia coli*. Ciprofloxacin was used as a bacterial positive control while fresh disc soaked in distilled water was used as a negative control and incubated at 37°C for 24 hours (Otokunefor and Dappa 2017).

3.8 Measurement of Zone of Inhibition.

The zone diameters were measured with the aid of meter rule and the average from each plate was calculated.

3.9 Determination of Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC).

MIC was determined for only the test that showed inhibitory activity according to the National Committee for Clinical Standard (1999). Nutrient broth was prepared and 1ml of the broth was transferred into 8 sterile test tubes 5 tubes for MIC and the remaining 3 for control (inoculum, sample and broth control). A concentration of 100% was prepared and added to the first tube, the working concentrations were serially diluted into the first four tubes containing the broth to give a concentration of 50%, 25%, 12.5% and 6.25% of the sample in the broth and this was done for all six samples respectively. Each test organism was inoculated into the labelled tube except the control tubes, the tubes were incubated at 37°C for 18-24hrs. The MIC was taken as the lowest concentration that prevented the visible growth.

3.1.0 Data Analysis

Statistically, the data generated were expressed using descriptive instrument and Percent expression after computation of RF applying the approved formula. Data were double entered into excel spread sheet (Excel version 5.0, Microsoft Excel), ANOVA was conducted using SPSS Version 28.0.1.1 (14) and results were expressed as a table.

CHAPTER FOUR
RESULTS

4.1 RESULTS

Table:1 Antibacterial Activity of Selected Hand Sanitizers Against *Escherichia coli*.

Sample	N	Baseline Activity	Reduction Activity
Instant	8	34±1	31±4
Cusson Carex	8	40±3	33±5*
Drug field	8	34±3	29±5
Liberate	8	33±3	24.4±6*

P = 0.02

Key: N=Total sample number, Mean values ± Standard deviation, * P<0.05

Table 2: Minimum Inhibitory Concentration

The table below shows the minimum inhibitory concentration of the sample against the test isolate where sample *Cusson curex* and *instant*.

Hand sanitizers	100(%)	50(%)	25(%)	12.5(%)
Instant	12.5	50.0	50.0	25.0
Cusson curex	25.0	12.5	12.5	25.0
Drug field	12.5	25.0	25.0	12.5
Liberate	25.0	12.5	12.5	25.0

Key: A= *E.coli* concentration at 100 percent dilution. B=at 50 C=25 D=12.5

CHAPTER FIVE

5.0 DISCUSSION

Hand sanitizers have been demonstrated to be widely effective against both gram positive and gram negative bacteria and other multi-resistant pathogens. A total of 4 brands hand sanitizers were purchased and 1 organism was collected from Umaru Musa 'Yaradua University Katsina state to determine the antibacterial effectiveness of the hand sanitizers. Organism used is *Escherichia coli*, were tested (a confirmatory test) in order to test the effectiveness of the sanitizers. The most effective hand sanitizers here are Sample Cusson carex and instant which have higher activity on *Escherichia coli*, this organism is resistant to liberate while drug field shows more activity on *Escherichia coli* which means it's effective to both gram positive and gram negative this result is in agreement with that of Sakuraji *et al* (1995) on similar studies which indicates that sanitizers with higher percentage of alcohol have more activities on gram negative organisms with reduced activity on gram positive organisms and samples with low to moderate percentage of alcohol have higher activities on both gram positive and gram negative.

The result for minimum inhibitory concentration shows that *E. coli* is inhibited at 12.5 and 25% and is killed at 25 and 50% concentrations. This result is in accordance with that of Kampf *et al* (1999), on similar studies. Cheesbrough 2006 also mentioned that microorganisms have different degree of susceptibility to antimicrobial agents. Hand sanitizer that contains at least 60% alcohol or contains a "persistent antiseptic" should be used. Alcohol rubs kill many different kinds of bacteria, including antibiotic resistant bacteria and TB bacteria. They also kill many kinds of viruses, including the flu virus, the common cold virus and coronaviruses 90% alcohol rubs are more effective against viruses than most other forms of hand washing. Isopropyl alcohol will kill 99.99% or more of all non-spore forming bacteria in less than 30 seconds, both in the laboratory

and on human skin. In too low quantities (0.3 ml) or concentrations (below 60%), the alcohol in hand sanitizers may not have the 10–15 seconds exposure time required to denature proteins and lyse cells. In environments with high lipids or protein waste (such as food processing), the use of alcohol hand rubs alone may not be sufficient to ensure proper hand hygiene.

5.1 Conclusion

Based on the research carried out it shows that hand wash and hand sanitizers are effective in reducing the bacteria load on hand. And it can be concluded that hand sanitizers that are more effective with regards to this research carried out on 4 different products Cusson curex and instant being the most effective brands among all the brands. Hand sanitizer is a disinfectant and therefore kills germs but it doesn't do anything to physically remove germs from a human skin like soap and water. Both substantive and non-substantive active ingredients can show a persistent effect if they substantially lower the number of bacteria during the wash or applied period. Alcohol-based hand sanitizer is more convenient compared to hand washing with soap and water in most situations in the healthcare setting. Among healthcare workers, it is generally more effective for hand antisepsis, and better tolerated than soap and water. Hand sanitizers have been heralded as an effective means to reduce bacterial burden and transmission in situations in which soap and water are unavailable to an individual. Hand sanitizers are more effective than plain soap and water alone in preventing transmission of bacteria from the hands of individuals. They play a significant role and could be an effective alternative to hand washing to achieve asepsis for all the health-care professionals in outreach program, water scarcity areas, and in routine clinical practice. Hence, stressing proper hand hygiene is an important first-line defense against the spread of multiple infectious diseases.

5.2 Recommendation

1. It is recommended that hand wash and hand sanitizers should be use together, especially by health care givers for effective removal/elimination of bacteria.
2. It is also recommend that the use of hand wash and sanitizers should be made a habit in our daily lives in order to reduce the risk of illness and spread of infections.
3. Manufacturers should increase the composition, concentration and consistency of products in order to improve its effectiveness.

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